

Thermodynamics of Complexation of 3,6-Dihydroxypyridazine with Manganese-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) Ions in 30% DMSO Media[†]

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Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method applied to diffusion currents in the polarographic study of complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^I and Zn^{II} with 3,6-dihydroxypyridazine yielded the following log K_1 and log K_2 values (298 K): Mn^{II} 7.77, 2.32; Co^{II} 7.20, 3.74; Ni^{II} 6.60, 4.11; Cu^I 10.48, 2.67; Zn^{II} 4.85, 3.62. The overall stability constants followed Irving-Williams natural order. Thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values in the range 288–308 K were all negative, proving the formation of strong complexes with greater order in their molecules.

Pyridazine derivatives are good sequestering agents. In particular pyridazine substituted by hydroxyl groups reacts readily with metal ions by the replacement of hydrogen ion of the hydroxyl group forming complexes. So far a number of complexes of different metal ions with substituted pyridazine derivatives have been reported¹ and their charge transfer studies, IR spectra and photochemical reactivities have been examined. Thermodynamic studies² of the dimethylpyridazine have been made and the thermodynamic functions free energy, enthalpy and entropy of the two steps of proton ionisations of *N,N'*-dimethylpyridazine, 2,6-dimethylpyridazine and *cis*-2,5-dimethylpyridazine were determined at 298 K in water and aqueous ethanol media at constant ionic strength (0.1N KNO₃).

In the present communication, the results of polarographic studies on complex-formation of 3,6-dihydroxypyridazine with some of the bivalent cations of the first transition period have been reported in 30% DMSO solutions and Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method^{3,4} has been applied to diffusion current for calculating the stability constants. Similar studies at three different temperatures (288, 298 and 308 K) have been made in order to calculate the thermodynamic parameters of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic and derived data are presented in Table 1. The well-defined diffusion-controlled cathodic waves have slopes of about 50 mV for the two-electron processes. As the $E_{1/2}$ values of the quasi-reversible waves of the complexes cannot be used to

determine the stability constants, Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method as applied to polarographic currents has been used instead. For this purpose changes in diffusion currents (Δi_d) in the presence of increasing ligand concentration have been plotted against log [L] and the sigmoidal pseudo-formation curves⁵ have been integrated to obtain a set of log F'_0 [L] values. From the limiting slopes of the plots of log F'_0 [L] vs log [L] and n_{max} (=2), the proportionality constant (k) values between $\bar{n}$ and Δi_d values are obtained. These are then used to obtain log F_0 [L] values from the respective log F'_0 [L] values. Plots of F_0 [L] vs log [L] give the F_1 [L] values and those of F_1 [L] vs log [L] give the F_2 [L] values and so on⁴.

The stability constants have also been computed (Table 2) using least-square method programme⁶ and these have been given in parenthesis. It is evident that the overall stability constants (log β_2) of the complexes follow the Mellor and Maley⁶ and Irving and Williams⁷ natural order: Mn < Co $\approx$ Ni < Cu > Zn. From the slopes of Arrhenius plots (log β_2 vs 1/T) for the complexes of 3,6-dihydroxypyridazine at three different temperatures, ΔG and ΔH values have been computed from changes in K values with changes in temperature and hence ΔS values have been obtained from them by conventional methods. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been obtained by least-square method as described earlier in the stability constant data. The ΔG and ΔH values are all negative indicating that the complexation process is spontaneous. The decrease in entropy values indicates higher order in the complex molecules.

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TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA ON COMPLEXATION OF M(II) WITH 3,6-DIHYDROXYPYRIDAZINE IN DMSO-WATER (30%) MEDIA (298 K) AT pH'S 6.4, 7.2, 6.8, 4.9 AND 8.0 FOR THE METAL IONS

M(II)=0.1 mmol dm⁻³, LiClO₄=0.1 mol dm⁻³, *m*=1.068 mg s⁻¹, *t*=4.3 s, *h*=70 cm/Hg

[L] mol dm ⁻³	$-E_{1/2}$ (Mn) V	$\bar{i}_d$ (Mn) A	$-E_{1/2}$ (Co) V	$\bar{i}_d$ (Co) A	$-E_{1/2}$ (Ni) V	$\bar{i}_d$ (Ni) A	$-E_{1/2}$ (Cu) V	$\bar{i}_d$ (Cu) A	$-E_{1/2}$ (Zn) V	$\bar{i}_d$ (Zn) A
0.000 00	1.36	0.77	1.30	1.58	1.13	1.04	0.02	0.64	1.21	0.98
0.000 01	1.37	0.69	1.31	1.46	1.15	0.94	0.03	0.56	1.24	0.72
0.000 05	1.38	0.61	1.32	1.40	1.16	0.72	0.04	0.50	1.26	0.67
0.000 10	1.39	0.60	1.33	1.30	1.18	0.68	0.05	0.50	1.29	0.60
0.000 50	1.41	0.58	1.35	1.26	1.20	0.59	0.05	0.48	1.30	0.59
0.001 00	1.44	0.55	1.37	1.22	1.21	0.58	0.06	0.47	1.31	0.56
0.002 00	1.45	0.53	1.39	1.16	1.22	0.48	0.07	0.40	1.32	0.54
0.005 00	1.46	0.53	1.40	1.12	1.23	0.45	0.08	0.32	1.34	0.52

log β_n values : (Mn)=10.09 ; (Co)=10.94 ; (Ni)=10.71 ; (Cu)=13.15 ; (Zn)=8.47.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH 3,6-DIHYDROXYPYRIDAZINE

Metal ion	Overall stability constants			298 K		
	288 K	298 K	308 K	$-\Delta G$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Mn ^{II}	10.38 (10.36)	10.09 (10.08)	9.68 (9.67)	42.326	61.810	-52.1
Co ^{II}	11.61 (11.60)	10.94 (10.93)	10.31 (10.30)	48.669	53.414	-44.3
Ni ^{II}	10.92 (10.90)	10.71 (10.72)	10.02 (10.03)	54.337	57.896	-61.2
Cu ^{II}	13.73 (13.74)	13.15 (13.16)	12.81 (12.82)	49.887	59.143	-37.9
Zn ^{II}	9.38 (9.36)	8.47 (8.48)	8.01 (8.00)	59.671	54.446	-29.8

Experimental

3,6-Dihydroxypyridazine (Aldrich), lithium hydroxide (B.D.H.), manganese, cobalt and zinc oxides, nickel and copper nitrates, perchloric acid and DMSO (all E. Merck) were used. The oxides and nitrates were converted to perchlorates, nitric acid being boiled off in the latter cases before crystallisation of the metal salts.

A Bruker E 310 universal modular polarograph in conjunction with a Hewlett-Packard 7050A X-Y recorder (scan rate, 5 mV s⁻¹; *m*, 1.068 mg s⁻¹; and *t*, 4.3 s for 70 cm/Hg), Julabo F-40 HC thermostat, Elico LI-120 pH-meter and double-walled Kalousek cell were used.

The test solutions comprised (a) metal-ClO₄ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm⁻³), LiClO₄ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mol dm⁻³), DMSO (3 ml), gelatin (1.0 ml, 0.05%) made upto 10 ml with double-distilled water and (b) metal ClO₄ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol dm⁻³), LiClO₄ (1.0 ml, 1.0 mmol

dm⁻³), gelatin (1.0 ml, 0.05%) increasing volumes of 3,6-dihydroxypyridazine in DMSO, additional DMSO to make the DMSO content to 3 ml and double-distilled water to make upto 10 ml. The pH's of the solutions were adjusted to appropriate values.

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